

DELIVERABLE REPORT

Grant Agreement Number: 101036401

Call identifier: H2020-LC-GD-2020-1

**Call Topic: LC-GD-2-3-2020 Accelerating the green transition and energy access
Partnership with Africa**

SteamBioAfrica

Innovative Large-Scale Production of Affordable Clean Burning Solid Biofuel and Water in Southern Africa: transforming bush encroachment from a problem into a secure and sustainable energy source

Deliverables: D1.4 Project Website

Project coordinator name	Professor Heike Knicker
Project coordinator organisation name	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas (CSIC)
Report prepared by	Colin Lindeque: Carbon Capital (Pty) Ltd Huw Parry: SteamBio Ltd

Version 3.0

Dissemination Level of Report

PU Public	X
PP Restricted to other program participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

PUBLIC

HISTORY OF CHANGES

Version	Date	Where	What: Brief description of change
2.0	06 February 2022	Cover page	Inclusion of EU logo with proper acknowledgement
3.0	02 May 2023	Acknowledgement	Inclusion of Legal disclosure (Disclaimer)

ABSTRACT

This deliverable report D1.4, Project Website, confirms that the project web site was designed and went live on 26th November 2021 on schedule. www.steambioafrica.com

This report includes the design of the look and feel of the project, including thematic colours, fonts, and a project logo. The website site map along with its functionality were then developed and populated with content. The website is now online and is undergoing search engine optimisation to maximise visibility.

The website will enable high visibility of the project and help to generate new leads. It will keep stakeholders and the public informed of project updates and related events and provide credibility to the project.

Table of Contents

Abstract	2
1 Overview	5
2 Logo development.....	5
3 Site Map.....	6
4 Website domain	8
5 Project Website.....	8
6 Compatibility & Accessibility.....	12
7 EU Acknowledgement	12
8 Social Media Integration.....	13
9 Backend access.....	13
10 Monitoring and evaluation	13
11 Conclusion.....	14
12 Acknowledgements & Legal Disclosure	14

1 OVERVIEW

The SteamBioAfrica project has an obligation to engage with stakeholders, inform the public, and publish related project articles and resources as per the European Union’s Horizon 2020 requirements. The project website will be the primary information dissemination platform to achieve the visibility, accessibility, and transparency of the project.

SteamBioAfrica also has aspirations beyond the project period and as such, the website is also aimed at generating commercial interest and attract future customers and/or partners.

The website www.steambioafrica.com went live 26th November 2021 ahead of schedule.

2 LOGO DEVELOPMENT

Prior to developing a website, the project required a design identity. The contracted website developers¹, with inputs from the project partners, underwent a comprehensive logo design process.

The process involved the selection of fonts, colours, layouts, and look and feel.

Figure 1: Logo development process; various design directions were considered.

¹ Website developer; V5 Digital, <https://www.v5.digital/>

Figure 2: Logo development; after shortlisting, the designs were refined.

Figure 3: Final project logo; available in both a horizontal and vertical formats to suit different media applications.

3 SITE MAP

The functionality and user interface of the website was developed keeping the primary objectives of visibility, accessibility, and transparency in mind.

The website site map was intentionally kept simple and intuitive, in order to be accessible to a wide audience. It comprises of a landing page (Home page) and five sub-pages (Project Overview, Partners, News, Resources, Contact).

Figure 4: Project website site map.

Website Pages

- **Home page;** the home page is the landing page of the project website, i.e. the first page visitors will arrive at. Being the first page, it needs to engage the audience within a short amount of time. It does this using short punchy text, imagery, and good design.

The Home page sets the scene of the project, giving a clear and broad understanding of the context of the project, the challenge statement, project goals, and important information, such as upcoming project events. The home page is intended to remain mostly static, apart from the important information. This ensures a consistent look and feel for the project and provides familiarity to repeat users.

- **Project Overview page;** the overview page dives deeper into the specifics of the project, including specific objectives and aspirations, operations and technology, and research areas.

The project overview page will be updated periodically where required. Visual media content will be added as the project operations and research commence.

PUBLIC

- **Partners page;** this page is used to acknowledge the project consortium partners, including short profiles elaborating their respective roles and expertise in relation to the project.

The page also serves to give visitors the chance to learn more about specific partners via their respective website links, as well as add credibility to the project, as the various partner logos will be familiar to many of the visitors.

- **News page;** this page serves to keep visitors up to date with related activities, milestones, and press releases. The news page will be complemented by the project's social media strategy and will ensure that project information is disseminated in a standardised and clear manner.

The news page will also act as a chronological reference of major project events.

- **Resources page;** this is the official project platform for publishing of public project reports and research publications. This page consolidates all related research findings, making it easy for research peers to access all the related research in one place.
- **Contacts page;** this page provides the contact details of the main project proponents as well as showing the location of project demonstration site.

4 WEBSITE DOMAIN

It was decided to host the project website on a neutral domain (.com vs .eu) as this is more reflective of the diverse group of partners within the project consortium.

As for the domain name, it was felt that a derivative website domain based on the project name was more sensible as opposed to an acronym (SteamBioAfrica vs SBA), as it would be less likely confused and mis-referenced with unrelated abbreviations and/or acronyms.

Hence, www.steambioafrica.com was decided to be the preferred domain and was secured accordingly.

5 PROJECT WEBSITE

The project website was developed using the site map structure, overlaid with design language reflective of the logo and available and relevant media content.

The project website uses images where possible to create negative space between portions of text, both enhancing digestibility of the content while also making for an engaging visual experience.

Figure 5: Home page; www.steambioafrica.com

Figure 6: Project overview page; <https://www.steambioafrica.com/project-overview>

Figure 7: Partners page; www.steambioafrica.com/partners

Figure 6: News page; <https://www.steambioafrica.com/news>

Figure 7: Resources page; <https://www.steambioafrica.com/resources>

Figure 8: Contact page; <https://www.steambioafrica.com/contact>

6 COMPATIBILITY & ACCESSIBILITY

It is essential that the website is compatible with different browsers and is accessible on various platforms and devices. The website is therefore optimised to be compatible on all of the major operating platforms, browsers, and device form factors.

It is also optimised for use in areas with lower speed internet, ensuring that it remains accessible within the southern African region.

Figure 9: Website compatibility with all the major operating platforms and browsers.

Figure 10: Optimised for accessibility on all devices.

7 EU ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The project website clearly recognises the EU funding that it has received, including the programme and grant agreement number.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036401

Figure 11: Website footer; featuring acknowledgement of the European Union's Horizon 2020 funding on every page of the website.

8 SOCIAL MEDIA INTEGRATION

Various social media platforms will in future be integrated along with the project website to both complement the website but also to broaden the visibility and reach of the project.

Social media platforms offer better engagement possibilities with the public and stakeholders, ensuring better accessibility and transparency.

The exact social media platforms to be integrated are still to be determined.

9 BACKEND ACCESS

The project website is constructed using the WIX framework, which is coupled to a user-friendly and intuitive backend with useful functionality.

This includes editing existing content, adding and removing content, uploading resources, monitoring downloads of resources, changing and/or adding media content, adding new articles and more.

Figure 12: Website backend on WIX platform.

10 MONITORING AND EVALUATION

The website platform is integrated with WIX Analytics, which is software that records the number of visitors the website receives, how long they spend on the site, whether they are newcomers or repeat visitors, what geographic areas they are accessing the website from, and more.

This tool can be used to track how many users the website is receiving, and from where. This can help inform the project team how best to optimise the communication and dissemination strategy, as well as offer valuable insight into the reach of the project.

11 CONCLUSION

We believe that we have developed a fit for purpose website that represents the SteamBioAfrica project in a balanced way.

The website is modern, engaging, and functional. It is a living platform and will grow and develop with the project.

It will provide visibility, transparency, and accessibility to the project.

12 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS & LEGAL DISCLOSURE

Acknowledgments:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036401.

Legal disclosure:

The sole responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Commission nor any person acting on behalf of the Commission is responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.